

SELF-CONDENSATION OF 3:4-DIHYDROCOUMARIN

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Dihydrocoumarin is shown to undergo self-condensation with the aid of sodium hydride, and the product has been converted into *bis(2:2')*-*spiro*-chroman.

*iso*Coumaranone (I) has been shown to undergo self-condensation with the aid of sodium alkoxides or better sodium hydride, affording 3-*o*-hydroxyphenylacetyl-coumaranone-2 (Chatterjea, this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 175; Geissman and Armen, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 1623). It was of interest to extend the reaction to the ring homologue, 3:4-dihydrocoumarin (II). Indeed, dihydrocoumarin underwent self-condensation with the aid of sodium hydride, yielding dimer, $C_{18}H_{16}O_4$, isolated through the copper chelate, together with a small quantity of a neutral compound, $C_{17}H_{16}O_2$, which was formed in a substantial quantity when an excess of the hydride was employed.

The self-condensation product is assigned the structure (III) (analogous to the self-condensation product of *isocoumaranone*) on account of the following facts: (i) the compound is phenolic, (ii) it shows a typical ferric reaction and as mentioned above, it affords a copper chelate, and (iii) on hydrolysis with acid the compound loses a molecule of carbon dioxide, forming a neutral compound, identical with the above mentioned compound, $C_{17}H_{16}O_2$, which, on the basis of the structure (III) for the self-condensation product, should be (IV) and indeed proved identical with an authentic specimen of spiran *bis(2:2')*-*spiro*-chroman, previously prepared by Borsche (*Ber.*, 1912, 45, 46) by the catalytic reduction of *bis(o*-hydroxybenzylidene)-acetone (V).

Dihydrocoumarin is much less reactive than *isocoumaranone*. Attempts to acylate the compound with sodium acetate-acetic anhydride under vigorous conditions afforded unchanged product (cf. Chatterjea, *loc. cit.*).

E X P E R I M E N T A L

3:4-Dihydrocoumarin was prepared by the catalytic reduction of coumarin in acetic acid in the presence of palladised charcoal or palladised barium sulphate (5%) at atmospheric pressure. The absorption of hydrogen was very rapid and the yield was nearly quantitative.

Self-condensation of Dihydrocoumarin.—Dihydrocoumarin (2.2 g.) was added to a suspension of an excess of sodium hydride (0.45 g.) in benzene (15 c.c.) and the mixture refluxed under nitrogen for 3 hours with usual precautions to exclude moisture. Hydrogen was evolved and a white precipitate separated. Excess of the hydride was eliminated with alcohol; ice-water was added and the alkaline layer drawn off, acidified and extracted with ether; the ether was removed and the residue left in contact with acetic acid. Colorless crystals of (IV) separating were crystallised from acetic acid in colorless needles, m. p. 107° , yield 0.3 g. (Found: C, 80.9, 80.9; H, 5.6, 5.9. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{16}O_2$: C, 80.9; H, 6.2%).

The compound is insoluble in boiling alkali and shows no ferric reaction. The filtrate was brought to p_H 7, extracted with ether (40 c.c.) and the ether solution shaken with a saturated solution of copper acetate for 1 hour. After removal of ether, the sludge of crystals was filtered, washed with alcohol and the greenish copper chelate (0.23 g.) crystallised from benzene in light green plates, m. p. 217° . (Found: C, 65.5; H, 5.0; Cu, 10.5. $C_{18}H_{16}O_2Cu$ requires C, 66.1; H, 4.6; Cu, 10.0%). The copper chelate is slightly soluble in alcohol and is fairly soluble in ether.

3-[β -(o-Hydroxyphenyl)propionyl]-chroman-2-one (III) was liberated from the copper chelate by stirring with H_2SO_4 (dil.) in presence of ether for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. On removing the ether the compound was obtained which crystallised from alcohol in colorless prisms, m. p. $150-51^{\circ}$. (Found: C, 72.5; H, 5.1. $C_{18}H_{16}O_2$ requires C, 72.9; H, 5.4%). With ferric chloride the compound developed a yellow colour, gradually turning violet. The diacetyl derivative was obtained as an oil which could not be crystallised.

Ketonic Hydrolysis.—The compound (III, 0.1 g.) was boiled with a mixture of acetic acid (1.5 c.c.) and HCl (conc., 1 c.c.) for 2 hours. Evolution of carbon dioxide took place and the resulting oil which solidified crystallised from alcohol in colorless leaflets, m. p. 107° , identical (mixed m. p.) with an authentic specimen of bis(2:2')-spiro-chroman. Borsche (*loc. cit.*) reported m. p. 110° for the compound; prepared according to Borsche's method by the hydrogenation of (V) with palladised charcoal, the compound had m. p. 107° after vacuum distillation and crystallisation from alcohol. The compound had no absorption (in alcohol) in U. V. region.

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